

Academic Preparation Kit

1st Small Scale Event for University Students

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Disclaimer

This Academic Preparation Kit was compiled for the 1st Small Scale Event for University Students of the European Youth Parliament Portugal, which will take place digitally, from the 7th to the 9th of May 2021.

Topic Overviews

The Topic Overviews are written by the Committee Chairpersons and serve as background material. They aim to identify the importance of the issue at hand, as well as the principal matters within it, the interconnections amongst the main actors in those matters and the actions already taken by them, while offering a short look at their possible future development. They are written with the intention of providing stimulating, yet neutral, introductions. It must be noted that the content of the Overviews does not reflect the positions of the EYP Portugal, who strongly encourages independent thinking, and are the sole responsibility of their authors. Likewise, while the National Selection Conference will be held under the patronage of various public entities, no claim is made that their views are in any way represented by the contents of this preparation kit.

Keywords

The non-exhaustive list of keywords intends to facilitate the search for information, may that be documents, news items or articles, through different types of search engines, news websites or encyclopaedias.

Links

Regarding the suggestions of research links, the list is by no means exhaustive. Also, several of the websites may contain relevant information other than the one cited herewith. Several links have been made available. Please note that the EYP Portugal is not responsible for the contents of the various websites; the texts, images and/or audio or video clips reflect the opinions of their authors, only.

Wishing you a good read and successful preparation.

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EU Explained

I. What is the EU?

The European Union (EU) is a unique economic and political partnership between 27 European countries called 'Member States' which, together, cover much of the continent. The EU was created in the aftermath of World War II to foster economic cooperation and, thereby, peace – the idea being that countries who trade with one another become economically interdependent and, as such, more likely to avoid conflict. The result was the European Economic Community (EEC), created in 1958, between six countries: Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg and the Netherlands. Since then, and following various **enlargements**, a large single market has been created and continues to develop toward its full potential.

On June 23rd, 2016, the United Kingdom decided by referendum to leave the European Union, which triggered a process which is often referred to as the 'Article 50 proceedings'. After negotiating the future relationship of the UK with the EU was affected, resulting in the UK leaving the Union in 2020 and, therefore, the EU currently has a total of 27 Member States.

From Economic to Political Union

What began as a purely economic union has evolved into an organisation spanning many policy areas, from development aid to environment. A name change from EEC to EU, in 1993, reflected exactly that. The EU is based on the rule of law: everything it does is founded on treaties (see below, under 'VI. The Treaties'), voluntarily and democratically agreed by all **Member States**. These binding agreements set out the EU's goals in its many areas of activity.

Mobility, Growth, Stability, Single Currency

The EU has delivered half a century of peace, stability and prosperity, helped raise living standards and launched a single European currency, the **Euro**.

Thanks to the abolition of border controls between the EU Member States located in the Schengen zone, people can travel freely throughout most of the continent, and it has become much easier to live and work abroad in Europe.

The single or 'internal' market is the EU's main economic engine, enabling most goods, services, money and people to move freely. It remains an objective to develop this market further.

Human Rights and Equality

One of the EU's main goals is to promote human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, both internally and around the world. Since the Treaty of Lisbon entered into force, in 2009, the **Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union** brings all these rights together in a single document. The EU's institutions are legally bound to uphold them, as are the governments of all Member States.

EU Explained

Transparent and Democratic Institutions

As it continues to grow, the EU remains focused on making its governing institutions more transparent and democratic. More powers are being given to the directly elected European Parliament, while national parliaments are being given a greater role, working alongside the European institutions. In turn, European citizens have an ever-increasing number of channels for taking part in the political process.

II. How does the EU work?

The institutional structure of the EU cannot be compared to that of any other international organisations (e.g., the North Atlantic Treaty Organization or the United Nations). It is neither a centralised unity like a nation state, nor does it imitate a relatively loose structure, such as the Commonwealth of Nations or a confederation like the United States of America – it is an organisation sui generis. The structure is unique and continuously developed. The Treaty of Lisbon marks the last big step in this process.

III. Main Institutions

3.1 Within the institutional triangle

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

The **European Commission** (EC) is the ‘executive’ power of the EU. One Commissioner is appointed by each Member State (with one, currently Ursula von der Leyen, being the President of the EC). The Commissioners are appointed by their respective Member States, approved by the European Parliament and put in charge of specific issues (e.g., Elisa Ferreira, the Spanish Commissioner, is responsible for Cohesion and Reforms).

The EC monitors the Member States’ and the Union’s adherence to the **acquis communautaire** (the ensemble of all EU legislation), represents the Union in its foreign relations (especially through one of its Vice-presidents, Josep Borrell Fontelles, who is also the **High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy**) and has the exclusive Right of Initiative - the right to propose laws. In the EU, the EC has the right to propose Regulations and Directives to the European Parliament and to the Council of the European Union.

The term ‘Commission’ is also used to refer to the full administrative body of over 20,000 staff members working in various **Directorates-General** (DGs) or services, each responsible for a particular policy area and headed by a Director-General, who reports directly to the President. The DGs draft laws, but their proposals become official only once the College of Commissioners adopts them during its weekly meetings.

EU Explained

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT

The **European Parliament** (EP) is the first part of the EU's legislative branch and consists of 751 Members of Parliament (MEPs) elected for five-year mandates by all EU citizens (over 18 years old, in Austria over 16). The first direct EP election was held in 1979 and the latest took place in 2014.

The EP is divided into seven large **political groups** plus several independent MEPs. The three largest are the European People's Party (EPP), followed by the Party of European Socialists (PES) and by the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats Party (ALDE). It works either in a big **plenary** or in its 20 **Standing Committees**, each responsible for specific issue areas. The EP shares its legislative competences with the Council of the European Union.

COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION (COUNCIL OF MINISTERS)

Also known as 'the Council', the **Council of the EU** is structured in issue-specific groups (**councils**) comprising the respective Ministers of the Member States (e.g., the Council for Justice and Home Affairs). The 'president' in office supplies the different councils with a Chairperson, with the exception of the council on Foreign Affairs, which is presided to by the High Representative.

The issue areas are mirrored in those of the EP (e.g., environment, education, economy, budget), with whom the Council shares its legislative competences. Additionally, the Council also has executive powers. The Member States holding the presidency work together in groups of three, called 'trios', a system that was introduced by the Treaty of Lisbon. The trio set long-term goals and prepared a common agenda determining the topics and major issues that will be addressed by the Council over an 18-month period. On the basis of this programme, each of the three countries prepares its own more detailed six-month programme. The current trio is made up of Germany, Portugal (the current president) and Slovenia.

3.2 Outside the institutional triangle

EUROPEAN COUNCIL

The **European Council** (no standard abbreviation is used) is an EU institution comprising the heads of state or government of the Member States, along with the Council's own President (Charles Michel, since December 2019) and the President of the European Commission (Ursula von der Leyen, since November 2019). The High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy takes part in its meetings. The European Council was established as an informal body in 1975; it became an official EU institution when the Treaty of Lisbon entered into force.

While the European Council has no formal legislative power, it is charged under the Treaty of Lisbon with defining "the general political directions and priorities" of the Union. It is thus the Union's strategic (and crisis-solving) body, acting as the collective presidency of the EU.

EU Explained

EUROPEAN CENTRAL BANK

The European Central Bank (ECB) is the central bank for the Euro and administers the monetary policy of the Euro Area, which consists of 19 Member States and is one of the largest currency areas in the world. It is one of the world's most important central banks. The bank was established by the Treaty of Amsterdam, in 1998, and is headquartered in Frankfurt, Germany. Since 2019 (and until 2027), the President of the ECB has been Christine Lagarde, former managing director of International Monetary Fund. The owners and shareholders of the European Central Bank are the central banks of the 27 Member States of the EU.

COURT OF JUSTICE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

The **Court of Justice of the European Union** (CJEU) is an EU institution that encompasses the whole judiciary. Seated in Luxembourg, it consists of two major courts and a number of specialised courts. The institution was originally established in 1952 as the Court of Justice of the European Coal and Steel Communities (as of 1958, the Court of Justice of the European Communities (CJEC)), changing to its current name with the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon. Its mission is to ensure that “the law is observed [...] in the interpretation and application” of the Treaties. The Court reviews the legality of the acts of any EU institution, ensures that the Member States comply with obligations under the Treaties and interprets EU law at the request of national courts. In order for a case to be brought to the CJEU, first the national legal measures applicable to the case must be exhausted, which means that no higher national appeal is possible.

It consists of two major courts: i) the **European Court of Justice** (created in 1952), the highest court in the EU legal system; ii) the General Court (created in 1988; formerly, the Court of First Instance).

3.3 Not an EU body!

COUNCIL OF EUROPE

The **Council of Europe** (CoE) is an international organisation promoting cooperation amongst all countries of Europe in the areas of legal standards, human rights, democratic development, the rule of law and cultural cooperation. It was founded in 1949, has 47 Member States with over 800 million citizens, and is an entirely separate body from the EU. The CoE does not make binding laws.

Its best-known bodies are the **European Court of Human Rights** (ECHR), which enforces the **European Convention on Human Rights**, and the **European Directorate for the Quality of Medicines**, which, through the European Pharmacopoeia Commission, sets the quality standards for pharmaceutical products in Europe. The Council of Europe's work has resulted in standards, charters and conventions

EU Explained

to facilitate cooperation between European countries.

Its statutory institutions are the Committee of Ministers (comprising the foreign ministers of each of its 47 Member States), the Parliamentary Assembly (composed of MPs from the parliaments of each Member State) and the Secretary General (Marija Pejčinović Burić).

IV. What can the EU do?

Exclusive competences – as per Article 2 (1) and Article 3 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)

In these areas, only the EU may legislate and adopt legally binding acts. Exceptions are possible if the EU empowers Member States to act, or with regard to the implementation of Union acts.

- The customs union, including an internal free trade area with common customs tariffs (Art. 31 TFEU).
- The monetary policy of the EU for the Member States whose currency is the euro, overseen by the European Central Bank and with certain precepts formulated in the Stability and Growth Pact (Art. 129 (3) and (4), Arts. 132, 138, 219 TFEU).
- Competition rules controlling state aid from national governments and the actions of companies necessary for the functioning of the internal market.
- A common international trade policy, e.g., a common position in international trade negotiations (Art. 207 TFEU).
- The conclusion of certain international agreements (Art. 3 (2) TFEU).
- Common commercial policy.
- The conservation of marine biological resources (part of the Common Fisheries Policy, Art. 38 (1) TFEU).

Shared EU competences – as per Article 2 (2) and Article 4 TFEU.

These are policy areas on which the Member States have agreed to act individually if the EU has not exercised (or planned to exercise) its competence. If a policy area is neither exclusive nor falls under supportive actions, it is a shared competence. Some examples are: i) internal market; ii) economic, social and territorial cohesion; iii) agriculture and fishing (except the conservation of marine biological resources); iv) social policy; v) transport; vi) environment, pollution and energy; vii) consumer protection; viii) area of freedom, Security and Justice.

Supporting, coordinating or complementary competences – as per Article 2 (5) and Article 6 TFEU.

The EU can financially support the actions of the Member States that have agreed to coordinate their domestic policies through the EU. This, however, does not entail harmonisation of regulations. These areas include: i) education, vocational training, youth and sport; ii) tourism; iii) administrative cooperation; iv) civil protection; v) protection and improvement of human health; vi) industry; vii) culture.

EU Explained

V. Legal Acts of the EU

While the EU can issue several types of legal acts, not all are fully binding for Member States. These acts, named according to their legal strength, are divided into:

Regulations – have to be strictly adhered to in all Member States and leave no room for adjustments during the implementation process.

Directives – provide a framework and give a certain policy direction, leaving the Member States with more flexibility and room for adjustments.

Decisions – always address certain recipients and are only valid for those specific countries/institutions.

Recommendations – without legal force, but negotiated and voted on according to the appropriate procedure, they are not binding for the Member States.

Opinions – similar to recommendations in that they have no legal force, but not voted on, simply emitted.

The European legislative procedure runs considerably longer than those of most Member States. In brief: the EC (which has the exclusive Right to Initiative), the Council and the EP decide if the proposal becomes a legal act after having discussed relevant details. General policy guidelines and statements, especially from the EP, are formulated in Resolutions. They can entail instructions for future procedures, as well as regulations, which are formally valid in the Member States. Legal acts passed by the EP and the Council enter into force once the national governments have transposed them into national law.

VI. The Treaties

To read more, and in greater detail, about the EU, please refer to the texts of i) the **Treaty of Lisbon**; ii) the **Treaty on European Union** (TEU); iii) the **Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union** (TFEU).

The Theme

The 1st Small Scale Event will revolve around the theme **"Social decency in globalization: post-pandemic"**.

Following the negative effect of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, there is an increase in the number of deaths worldwide, while causing an extraordinary depletion in public health, food systems, economy, and environment.

Specifically, tens of millions of people are at risk of falling into extreme poverty, while the number of undernourished people, currently estimated at nearly 690 million, could increase by up to 132 million by the end of the year.

The impact of COVID-19 on people's livelihoods, health, and food supply but also the combination of employment issues, mental health issues, the risk to workers' health and safety, border closures, trade restrictions, and confinement measures are some of the consequences of the pandemic that people face.

Therefore, how can society thrive post-pandemic? What will happen to education equality? Will low-income nations get left behind in the race to procure a vaccine? How do we address the social problems that contributed to Covid-19? How can we prioritize mental health through policy and in our communities? How can we fight Covid-era loneliness? Could the pandemic boost international co-operation? How can countries adapt priorities to a post-Covid world? These are questions with millions of answers.

Therefore, it is time for people to emphasize global solidarity and support, especially with the most vulnerable in our societies. Only together can we overcome the intertwined health, social and economic impacts of the pandemic and prevent its escalation into a protracted humanitarian and food security catastrophe, with the potential loss of already achieved development gains.

Faced with these consequences and struggles, we must rethink the future with ambition and urgency. Only then can we protect the health, livelihoods, food security, and nutrition of all people, and ensure that our 'new normal' is a better one.

Committee Topics

DEVE - Committee on Development

Equitable access to vaccines and vital medicines across countries

The current pandemic has highlighted the inequalities in access to medicines and vaccines for developing countries. How can the EU ensure equitable global access to the medicines and vaccines being developed to mitigate the impact of the pandemic?

By Alyssa Mia Taliotou

EMPL - Committee on Employment and Social Affairs

Universal Basic Income

With the current pandemic increasing the uncertainty around citizens' incomes, the concept of a Universal Basic Income (UBI) has gained more traction. Taking into account the trials undertaken both prior to and during the pandemic, what should the stance of the EU and other European countries be towards this scheme?

By Leon Cummins

ENVI - Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety

Energy consumption & Greenhouse gas emissions

With the travel restrictions posed by the pandemic, a dramatic reduction in travel and economic activity has in consequence led to the energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions to have fallen sharply. Taking into account the 2030 climate and energy framework, what measures can the EU take to keep the low emissions and maintain a sustainable environment?

By Pedro Matos

Committee Topics

DROI - Committee on Human Rights

Refugees' physical and mental healthcare needs

With the COVID-19 posing a big challenge for many of Europe's healthcare systems and disproportionately affecting vulnerable communities such as refugees, their access to medical care is further hindered by practical obstacles such as language barriers and improper reception facilities. What measures should be taken by the Member States to safeguard the physical and mental healthcare needs of asylum seekers, and to also ensure unhindered access to other essential services following their arrival in the EU?

By Lazar Tripinovic

FEMM - Committee on Women's Rights and Gender Equality

Domestic Violence & Gender Equality

Cry for help: Domestic violence has elevated during lockdown with the European Commission noting a dramatic increase in reports by 60% around Europe. How can the EU protect women's human rights and gender equality during a pandemic?

By Stefanos Francis

CULT - Committee on Culture and Education

Effect of the pandemic on education

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected educational systems worldwide, leading to the near-total closures of schools, universities and colleges with over 100 million children falling below the minimum proficiency level in reading as a result of the health crisis. What measures can be taken by the Member States to ensure that the youth will receive the best academic level possible during the pandemic?

By Beatriz Soares

DEVE

Committee on Development

Equitable access to vaccines and vital medicines across countries

The current pandemic has highlighted the inequalities in access to medicines and vaccines for developing countries. How can the EU ensure equitable global access to the medicines and vaccines being developed to mitigate the impact of the pandemic?

By Alyssa Mia Taliotou

Topic Overview

Committee on Development (DEVE)

The current pandemic has highlighted the inequalities in access to medicines and vaccines for developing countries. How can the EU ensure equitable global access to the medicines and vaccines being developed to mitigate the impact of the pandemic?

Chairperson: Alyssa Mia Taliotis (CY)

Topic in a nutshell

The **COVID-19¹ pandemic** has caused substantial **excess mortality** and plunged national **economies** into deep recessions, whilst destructing the peace of **mental health** and sanity. It is also apparent that the COVID-19 pandemic has no foreseeable end unless there is a global rollout of **vaccines** that will protect all people against severe disease and develop strong immune systems. This disease has put a major pause in world development, progress, trade, human connection, and livelihood, and the anguish to return to life before the pandemic has become a unified **global priority**.

Thus, many countries around the world have [authorised COVID-19 vaccines for human use](#) in 2020, and numerous more countries are proceeding with licensing them in 2021. However, licensed vaccines are not enough to achieve global control of COVID-19 when they are still **not accessible** to a large part of the world's population.

[Low accessibility rates](#) have root causes in the small-scale production of the vaccines, the **unaffordable price**, and the **limited availability** in developing countries where they are needed. Furthermore, in many of these developing countries such as [Tanzania and Madagascar](#), there is still dispute about the plain existence of the virus and the necessity of the vaccine.

But what other reasons are behind the slow roll-out of these preventative treatments? Why is there still **hesitancy** about the vaccine specifically for a disease that has **killed more than 3,085,954 people**? Is the EU doing enough? What can be done to secure **health security** to its population, to increase production, deployment, and accessibility rates? How can the EU contribute to ending this pandemic that is scouring the global state?

¹ **Coronavirus disease (COVID-19)** is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus.

Key Terms

- A **pandemic** is defined as an epidemic², as in a disease outbreak, that reaches global dimensions.
- **Personal protective equipment (PPE)** is the equipment worn by healthcare professionals in order to minimize their exposure to hazards that cause serious workplace injuries and illnesses.
- **Private market** consists of the investments in equity and debt of privately-owned companies.
- **Vaccines** are biological preparations that provide active acquired immunity to a particular infectious disease.
- **Types of COVID-19 vaccine:**
 - [Whole Virus Vaccine \(Sinopharm, Sinovac\)](#) is a weakened or deactivated form of the pathogen that causes a disease to trigger protective immunity to it.
 - [RNA or mRNA Vaccine \(Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna\)](#) teaches our cells how to make a protein that triggers an immune response inside our bodies.
 - [Non-replicating Viral Vector Vaccine \(Oxford-Astra Zeneca, Sputnik V\)](#) is unable to make new viral particles but they produce the vaccine antigen.
 - [Protein Subunit Vaccine \(Novavax\)](#) contains fragments of protein and/or polysaccharide from the pathogen, which these molecules are likely to produce a strong and effective immune response.

Stakeholders & Measures in place

The [World Health Organisation \(WHO\)](#) is a specialised agency of the [United Nations \(UN\)](#)³ responsible for International Public Health⁴. Their main objective is the attainment by all people of the highest possible level of health. They play a major role in **assuring the quality of all vaccines** that could be purchased by UN agencies reviewing the quality, safety, and efficacy data.

² An **epidemic** is a widespread occurrence of an infectious disease in a community at a particular time.

³ The **United Nations (UN)** is an intergovernmental organization that aims to maintain international peace and security, develop friendly relations among nations, achieve international cooperation, and be a centre for harmonizing the actions of nations.

⁴ **Public health** is defined as the health of the population as a whole, especially as the subject of government regulation and support.

[COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access Facility \(COVAX\)](#) is a global initiative aimed at **equitable access** to COVID-19 vaccines led by [Gavi the Vaccine Alliance](#)⁵, the [Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations \(CEPI\)](#)⁶, and the World Health Organization.

[Access to COVID-19 tools Accelerator \(ACT\)](#) is a groundbreaking global collaboration led by WHO, Gavi, and CEPI, to accelerate **development, production, and equitable access to COVID-19 tests, treatments, and vaccines.**

[European Commission](#) is the executive branch of the European Union, responsible for proposing legislation, implementing decisions, upholding the EU treaties, and managing the day-to-day business of the EU. On 14 April, the [European Commission reached an agreement with BioNTech-Pfizer](#) to speed up the delivery of vaccines. [50 million additional doses](#), initially foreseen for the fourth quarter of 2021, will be delivered in the second quarter, starting in April.

[International Coalition of Medicines Regulatory Authorities \(ICMRA\)](#) is a voluntary, executive-level, strategic coordinating, advocacy, and leadership entity of regulatory authorities that aims to expedite and streamline the development of COVID-19 vaccines and treatments. In April 2020, [ICMRA members](#) are committed to **strengthening global collaborative efforts** to align the facilitation of rapid development, approval, and global roll-out of safe and effective medicines and vaccines to prevent and treat COVID-19.

[Council for International Organisations of Medical Sciences \(CIOMS\)](#) is an international, non-governmental, non-profit organization established jointly by WHO and [UNESCO](#)⁷ in 1949. Its mission is to **advance public health** through guidance on health research and policy including ethics, medical product development, and safety. The CIOMS guide to [active vaccine safety surveillance](#) published in 2017 will be used for guidance for COVID-19 vaccine safety monitoring.

[United Nations Children's Fund \(UNICEF\)](#) is a United Nations agency responsible for providing **humanitarian and developmental aid to children worldwide.** UNICEF is expected to [provide support](#) to the immunization programmes in countries for vaccination activities and distribution of COVID-19 vaccines.

⁵ **Gavi the Vaccine Alliance** is a public-private global health partnership with the goal of increasing access to immunisation in poor countries.

⁶ **The Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI)** is a foundation that takes donations from public, private, philanthropic, and civil society organisations, to finance independent research projects to develop vaccines against emerging infectious diseases.

⁷ **UNESCO** is a specialised agency of the United Nations aimed at promoting world peace and security through international cooperation in education, the sciences, and culture.

Key challenges

The COVID-19 pandemic is a public health issue that threatens **health security, increases healthcare costs, damages the economy**, and increases the mortality rate;

Firstly, the [augmentation of vaccine production](#) is a challenge due to the non-existent chain production networks. With too many production companies and no unified order to follow the vaccines are being produced to a limited amount which is correlated with the persistence of several Member States to [reproduce their own vaccines](#).

The inadequate amount of vaccines results in raising concerns that their acquisition will be from the **few and the wealthy** in many countries. Vaccine manufacturers have started to sell in [private markets](#) at premium prices. Likewise, High-Income Countries (HICs) constitute [82% of global vaccine sales](#) in terms of value. Not only do they offer higher prices but they are more likely to implement newer vaccines. With HICs offering high rates, developing countries are unable to reach the market sale price.

Furthermore, vaccine production companies such as Pfizer are focusing on their own economic growth rather than common health and have begun **bargaining** with countries like [Brazil](#), only offering them vaccines in exchange for their oil and other natural resources. Such acts have led these countries to reject the vaccinations thus constituting the vaccination process even slower.

Depending on the duration of the protection offered by the vaccine, the already unaffordable preventative treatment will potentially require modified vaccines against [new variants of the virus](#).

Some companies such as AstraZeneca and Johnson & Johnson, which are benefiting heavily from public-sector investments, have **pledged to sell their vaccines globally at low prices**. Both companies have committed to maintaining these prices during the pandemic, although more clarity is needed on how the [price scales](#) for COVID-19 vaccines and other treatments will follow post-pandemic.

In addition, in most Member States the first income of vaccines are aimed at the **elderly populations** who have been proven to have a [higher risk](#) of disease when catching the virus. With an average of 41% of the elderly population being [vaccinated](#). However, the vaccines have only been approved for [mostly the adult population with Johnson & Johnson and the Moderna vaccine being approved for use in persons over 18 years of age with the exception of the Pfizer vaccine that has been authorised for persons over 16 years of age](#).

Although the EU aims to have 70% of the population vaccinated by July, studies show that 51% of the European population will either [reject or delay their COVID-19 vaccination](#). This issue is a consequence of the ongoing **uncertainty around the safety of the vaccine** which many believe has not been tested for an adequate amount of time in order to prove effective and not harmful. They support that it is premature and not yet trustworthy to insert the human body.

Another major challenge is the **global inequality in accessing COVID-19 vaccines**. Scarcity in supply coupled with the large volumes of pre-orders made by richer countries creates challenges to achieving timely, universal access. Uneven access to vaccines would not be unprecedented as seen in the 2009 H1N1 outbreak⁸. To avoid a repetition of the scenario, the WHO announced the creation of a **global allocation mechanism**, the COVID-19 Vaccine Global Access (COVAX) Facility, coordinated jointly with CEPI and Gavi seeking to **secure lower prices and provide all countries with access to vaccines** to administer to [20% of their population](#). Nonetheless, for COVAX to succeed, it needs substantial funding to purchase vaccines and **a threat to equitable allocation** comes from national procurement strategies that might leave COVAX with inadequate supply. With only 8 countries having vaccinated [over 50% of their population and 153 countries having not](#) (including 11 countries that have vaccinated less than 0.1% of their population) the **COVAX method is proving unsuccessful**.

Beyond the economic aspect, there is also an issue with the deployment of the vaccines as the rapid pace of production and development has [shortened the time available](#) for national, regional, and local health officials to plan **training and preparedness for COVID-19 vaccination programmes**.

Lastly, the **lack of data about PPE availability** has proven a great challenge. The WHO has called on industry and [governments to increase manufacturing by 40%](#) to meet rising global demand as panic buying, hoarding and misuse of PPE is putting lives at risk from the new coronavirus. Shortages are leaving **doctors, nurses and other frontline workers dangerously ill-equipped** to care for COVID-19 patients, due to [limited access to supplies](#) such as gloves, medical masks, gowns, and aprons and medical professionals in India have even attempted to use helmets, plastic bags, and raincoats as protective gear amidst PPE shortage.

Outlook

Currently, the EU and its Member States are facing major backlash from the COVID-19 pandemic and its consequences. Its citizens are unemployed, its children are remaining uneducated and chaos is rising. With several lockdowns keeping people locked at home, they have plenty of time to develop **hesitancy** about receiving the vaccine for the COVID-19 pandemic even after it has killed millions of

⁸The **2009 H1N1 swine flu pandemic** was an influenza pandemic that lasted about 19 months, from January 2009 to August 2010, and was the most recent flu pandemic involving H1N1 influenza virus.

An infographic taken from the [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention \(CDC\)](https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/vaccines).

people. But where is the **reassurance**? Religious objections have begun reappearing because of previous known racist experimentation for medical research. The most important factor is that **accurate information is available**. Why are healthcare organisations and vaccine manufacturers not providing **free or cost-efficient vaccinations** and why are **economic strategies** falling more important than global health even whilst more than 85 poor countries will not have widespread access to coronavirus vaccines before 2023? Can the EU efficiently ensure **equitable global access** to the vaccine and other medical treatments aiming to defeat this pandemic? A crisis as such has overtaken civil society and the economy and a bright future seem uncertain. This crisis is a foundation for the global state to **construct resilience mechanisms** to overcome both the COVID-19 pandemic and future crises. The question is WHO will be brave enough to rise to the challenge of the new era?

Further Readings

Audiovisual:

- [The antigen podcast, Lindsey Dietschi](#), A podcast mini-series that gives accurate information and updates on the global response to the pandemic, where Pfizer scientists and experts from UNICEF and more, come along to speak about this public health problem.
- [COVAX: Ensuring global equitable access to COVID-19 vaccines](#), A very small video on providing equitable access to COVID-19 vaccines.
- [Covid-19: what will it take to vaccinate the world? |The Economist](#), A small video with the challenges of vaccinating the global population.
- [Will it be safe? Vaccine safety science from Cowpox to COVID-19 | Helen Petousis-Harris | TEDxUOA](#), A TEDtalk on the safety and ideology of safety around the COVID-19 vaccine.
- [Podcast: Educating patients on the COVID-19 vaccine with Dr. Joseph Cacchione](#), A podcast with suggestions on how to educate the global population about the COVID-19 vaccine.

Data:

- [COVID-19 Vaccine | A look at how vaccination is affecting death rates across the world, Money Control](#), Data on the pre-vaccination and post-vaccination death rates.
- [Coronavirus \(COVID-19\) Vaccinations, Our World In Data](#), Data on the global vaccination rates.

Publications:

- [Challenges in ensuring global access to COVID-19 vaccines: production, affordability, allocation, and deployment, Olivier J Wouters & others](#), A paper on the main challenges in ensuring global access to the vaccine.
- [Improving global vaccine accessibility, Andrew B Hill & Others](#), A paper on proposals of vaccine accessibility improvement.

EMPL

Committee on Employment and Social Affairs

Universal Basic Income

With the current pandemic increasing the uncertainty around citizens' incomes, the concept of a Universal Basic Income (UBI) has gained more traction. Taking into account the trials undertaken both prior to and during the pandemic, what should the stance of the EU and other European countries be towards this scheme?

By Leon Cummins

Topic Overview

Committee on Employment and Social Affairs (EMPL)

With the current pandemic increasing the uncertainty around citizens' incomes, the concept of a Universal Basic Income (UBI) has gained more traction. Taking into account the trials undertaken both prior to and during the pandemic, what should the stance of the EU and other European countries be towards this scheme?

Chairperson: Leon Cummins (IE)

Topic in a nutshell

It's safe to say that the current pandemic has caused a massive ripple effect within our society. With millions of people having [lost their jobs](#) due to COVID-19 across the globe, the discussion around Universal Basic Income (UBI) and its implementation have rapidly gained momentum as of recent months. However, what exactly is UBI? Universal Basic Income is a **wealth redistribution system where the government supplies a set sum of money every month to each and every citizen of a country**. But why has not this already been implemented? Well, the debate around the implementation of UBI has been a controversial one even before the ongoing pandemic, causing mass confusion as to how it would be implemented and how it would affect the economy as a whole. However, [UBI has been shown](#) to have many positive impacts on not only the quality of living for citizens but economic growth as a whole.

There are many benefits to UBI which have been made more apparent through the recent pandemic. With so many people having been displaced from their places of employment, many have argued that UBI could help to [ease the financial stress](#) of citizens during trying times by providing them a financial safety net to support themselves. However, that's not to say that it is without its flaws. UBI most certainly is not cheap and so its implementation would involve a **redistribution of income from upper to lower social classes**, leading to an increase in the taxes on large multinational companies likely proposed by politicians such as Andrew Yang.

Regardless of these issues, many agree that the EU should strive to support all Member States and their citizens during the COVID-19 pandemic and UBI is one of the many options which have recently

been brought to the table, but the real question is how can the EU maintain our economic growth while implementing UBI to support all citizens?

Key Terms

Universal/Unconditional Basic Income (UBI) is a governmental programme in which every adult citizen receives a set amount of money on a regular basis with the goal of alleviating poverty and improving social benefit systems.

Globalisation is defined by the [European Commission](#)¹ as “the combination of technological progress, lower transport costs and policy liberalization in the European Union and elsewhere” that “has led to increasing trade and financial flows between countries”.

Income Inequality is defined as how uneven the distribution of income is within a nation amongst its different social classes.

COVID and the economy - Many economists were in agreement that the global economy would take a hit from COVID-19, predicting that [2020 would foresee a 2.9% loss in GDP](#) which was unfortunately restated later on to being a GDP loss of 4.5%, making it a prevailing issue over the last year.

Automation is the automatic production of goods through the utilization of robotics, control systems, and other processes with the little direct human operation.

Economic Growth is the process by which the production of goods and services increases over a specific period. Economic growth leads to more profit for businesses which in turn leads to more employment opportunities, a rise in income, and an increase in the price of goods and services.

Stakeholders & Measures in place

The European Commission - The European Commission is an executive branch of the European Union and is responsible for the proposition and implementation of different legislation across the EU.

The European Parliament - The European Parliament is a part of the legislative process of the EU. Most proposed laws in the EU must be passed within the European Parliament as one of the initial steps.

¹You can find the definition of the European Commission in the **‘Stakeholders & Measures in place section’**.

EU Member States - The EU is made up of 27 different countries, more commonly known as “Member States”. These countries are all involved in a diverse mix of treaties and agreements across the EU and all have representatives within the different bodies of the EU.

Unconditional Basic Income Europe (UBIE) is an international non-profit organisation that has members from over 30 European countries who advocate for the **implementation of UBI across Europe** and that it be recognised as a **Universal Human Right**². They strive to popularise the discussion around UBI across Europe and to address the concerns around UBI in order to make it a “credible and attractive alternative” for all European countries. Because of their efforts and campaigning, UBI is slowly becoming a more heavily discussed topic within the EU and has been gaining popularity amidst the pandemic.

Recovery plan for Europe - With the COVID-19, there is a devastating economic impact over the last year, the EU has created an economic plan which will **strive to support modernisation and improve the fight against climate change**. Within the recovery plan, the largest stimulus package that has ever been created within an EU budget resides, totaling **1.8 trillion euros with the purpose of rebuilding a post-COVID Europe and making Europe both greener and more digital in turn**. This plan was created by the European Commission, European Parliament, and the Member States and also includes EU economic instruments such as “**Next Generation EU**”³.

Recovery Assistance for Cohesion and the Territories of Europe (REACT-EU) is a project which is being forwarded by the European Commission and has amassed a total of 47.5 billion euros. This money will be used to “**repair the crisis response and crisis repair measures**” and is an instrument that the EU will use to further **help the Member States to recover from the economic shifts** caused by the pandemic. It takes into account the **rise of unemployment, GDP drop**⁴, and the **proportionate wealth of other countries**.

Key challenges

- **UBI’s implementation** - Another question that has been raised during the discussion around UBI is **how it would function** and where would a government get the money for it? Many proposals have been made as to how we can redistribute income without causing a drastic

²A **Universal Human Right** is a human right which is recognised under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, a declaration created by the UN which consists of the fundamental human rights that are recognised across all UN members.

³ **Next Generation EU** is a European recovery instrument of 750 billion euro which aims to address the social and economic damage which will be brought upon the EU after the current pandemic.

⁴ A **GDP drop** is when the total value of a country’s goods and services over the course of a specific time period decreases.

increase in citizens' taxes, but one of the many solutions proposed was brought to the table by the American politician **Andrew Yang**. [Yang believes](#) that a new tax should be introduced for multinational companies which would subsequently contribute to the income of consumers, thus encouraging more sales for those companies. He also believes that the reduced spending on homelessness and incarceration due to the improved mental health of citizens would also contribute to offsetting the costs. With so many options on the table in regards to the implementation of UBI, how should the EU go about this if that decision were to be made?

- **Misconceptions around the incentive to work** - One of the main criticisms around the implementation of UBI is that the sum of money will **discourage unemployed people** from looking for a new place of employment, causing a reduction in a country's workforce. It is also believed that the lack of a job would impact an individual's personal wellbeing since they are being deprived of the "meaning to life" that employment grants. However, [studies](#) have shown that the effect that UBI has on a person's want to work was practically non-existent when compared with the increase in wages that they received. Knowing this, what can the EU do in order to tackle the stigma around the effect that UBI would have on the workforce of a country?
- **Addressing the Economic Factors** - Another argument which is commonly made against UBI is that the redistribution of income that UBI entails would create an "**absolute zero**" in the economy, meaning that it would change nothing since every citizen gets the same amount of money which would lead to an increase in prices. However, since no new money is being printed and instead [the income is being redistributed](#) from the upper class back down to the middle and lower classes, prices would barely shift. Knowing this, what systems could the EU put in place to ensure that the implementation of UBI won't cause mass inflation while also educating people on its economic repercussions?

Outlook

As we all know, COVID-19 has affected all of our lives in borderline irreparable ways. **Millions across the world have been displaced from their jobs** and this past year has taken a toll on the **overall well-being of our populations**. However, not all hope is lost. The potential implementation of UBI in the future is a massive step in returning back to normal and helping people to support themselves through such trying times. Although UBI certainly has its critiques and flaws that need to be avoided and improved upon, the bottom line is that **the EU needs to provide its citizens with economic support before we can mentally recover from the pandemic**. With this, what do you think should be done to help to improve upon UBI and COVID-19 relief? Do you think that UBI is a good idea for

implementation? And finally, how do you think UBI would help those who you know that have lost their jobs amidst the pandemic, and do you, therefore, believe that its introduction would be worth it?

Further Readings

Audiovisual:

- [What gives a dollar its value? ,TED-Ed](#), A video by Doug Levinson around the basics of inflation, deflation, and the economy.
- [Andrew Yang on UBI and Human-Centered Capitalism,CNBC](#), An interview with American politician Andrew Yang around his ideas of UBI and his view on our capitalist society.
- [Universal Basic Income or Universal Basic Services?,New Economics Foundation](#), A podcast starring different economists centered around the implementation and structure of UBI.

Articles & Publications:

- [Result of Finland's Basic Income Experiment, Kela](#), A summarization of the two-year study carried out in Finland around UBI.
- [What we know about Universal Basic Income, Stanford Basic Income Lab](#), A study that cross-references different studies around UBI and its potential implementation.

ENVI

Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety

Energy consumption & Greenhouse gas emissions

With the travel restrictions posed by the pandemic, a dramatic reduction in travel and economic activity has in consequence led to the energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions to have fallen sharply. Taking into account the 2030 climate and energy framework, what measures can the EU take to keep the low emissions and maintain a sustainable environment?

By Pedro Matos

Topic Overview

Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI)

With the travel restrictions posed by the pandemic, a dramatic reduction in travel and economic activity has in consequence led to the energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions to have fallen sharply. Taking into account the 2030 climate and energy framework, what measures can the EU take to keep the low emissions and maintain a sustainable environment?

Chairperson: Pedro Matos (PT)

Topic in a nutshell

In the mid 18th century, with the Industrial Revolution, humans realised the infinite possibilities that amounted to simply transforming energy. [The invention of the steam engine, which simply transforms chemical stored energy into heat, and then uses that heat to produce work, set the basis for all the technological revolution that would come in the following two and a half centuries.](#) It enabled the creation of big industries, modified the way people moved with its implementation on cars and trains, it powered machines through large-scale agriculture, etc. We have been using its successor, the combustion engine, for more than a century now, to power us through a truly globalised world. However, only recently did we realise that we have been harming our planet, causing the climate to warm up and destroying entire biomes and that **we might not have that much time to prevent irreversible damage.**

According to the **2018 IPCC special report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C**, [global warming has reached 1°C above pre-industrial level and is expected to continue growing at a rate of around 0.2°C per decade, unless drastic changes to our lifestyles and economic systems are made.](#)

In the past year, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, we have witnessed an unprecedented drop in human activity, as much of the world went into successive lockdowns and factories stopped operating, cars kept their engines off and planes were grounded. Nevertheless, in both the short and long term, the **pandemic will have less effect on efforts to tackle climate change** than many people had hoped. Even though [the world experienced a drop of about 7% in gross emissions of greenhouse gases](#), it

is expected that [the global temperature will only be about 0.01°C lower in 2030 as a consequence of this period.](#)

The temporary halt to normal life that we have experienced in the past year is, besides not very effective, not a sustainable strategy to tackle climate change. Instead, a collective plan of action addressing transportation, energy production, agriculture, waste management, deforestation, and the economy, among other areas, simultaneously, is the only solution to pave the way for a greener and more sustainable future.

Key Terms

- **Greenhouse Gases (GHGs)** are gases that contribute to the greenhouse effect. Some examples include Water Vapor (H₂O), Carbon Dioxide (CO₂), Nitrous Oxide (N₂O), and Methane (CH₄).
- **The Greenhouse Effect** is caused by the accumulation of Greenhouse Gases in the atmosphere. These gases radiate part of the infrared radiation emitted by the Earth back to the Earth's surface, causing its temperature to be higher than it would be without an atmosphere. Although a natural and indispensable phenomenon, [its increase is the main cause of Global Warming.](#)
- **Global Warming** is a gradual increase in the overall temperature of the Earth's atmosphere.
- **Renewable Energy**, often referred to as **Clean Energy** or **Alternative Energy**, is a type of energy obtained through sustainable sources. This means that they are naturally replenished at a higher rate than human consumption.
- **Carbon Neutrality** means a balance between the net carbon emitted and the carbon that can be absorbed by Nature's sinks.
- **Green Economy** refers to an economic system where growth and development are sought through sustainable and environmentally responsible practices while supporting progress on social development.
- **Carbon Tax** is a fee imposed on the burning of carbon-based fuels. It is one of the most common and most effective measures to decrease the emissions of carbon dioxide.

Stakeholders & Measures in place

[The European Commission \(EC\)](#) is an executive branch of the European Union (EU) that is responsible for legislation proposal and decision implementation, such as **2020, 2030, and 2050 climate and energy frameworks.**

[The 2030 Climate and Energy Framework](#) includes EU-wide targets and policy objectives for the period from 2021 to 2030. Some of the key objectives for 2030 include the reduction of at least 40% of greenhouse gas emissions in comparison to 1990 levels, at least 32% of the overall energy production to be originated from renewable sources, and at least a 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency.

[The 2050 Long-Term Strategy](#) expresses the EU's aim to be **the first carbon-neutral continent** by 2050. It indicates what should be the main areas of focus of the EU to attain this objective: invest in realistic technological solutions, empower citizens and align actions in key areas such as industrial policy, finance, and research, while ensuring social fairness for a just transition.

[The European Green Deal](#) provides a roadmap to move to a clean and circular economy, by improving efficiency in resource usage, restoring biodiversity, and cutting on pollution. It proposes the [European Climate Law](#) to turn the political commitment of being climate-neutral by 2050 into a legal obligation for all the Member States. It has also proposed the European Commission a further reduction from 40% to 55% in all Greenhouse Gas emissions by 2030, ambitiously expanding the goal defined by the 2030 Climate and Energy Framework.

[The EU Member States \(MS\)](#) are all part of the bigger picture of getting to grips with Climate Change. They can legislate individually in order to achieve the targets defined by the EU regarding the transition to clean energy and a green economy.

[The European Environment Agency \(EEA\)](#) is an EU agency responsible for providing independent data and producing assessments on a wide range of topics related to the environment to both policymakers and the general public.

[The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change \(IPCC\)](#) is the United Nations (UN) body for assessing the scientific basis of climate change, its risks, and impacts, as well as what decisions could be made so as to address it and mitigate its effects.

Key challenges

According to UN specialists, [we only have nine more years to prevent irreparable damage to the environment](#). Climate change has already been impacting disparately different sectors of society, with people with lower net income being harmed the most. A swift response to the challenges posed by the climate threat is urgent. However, some proposed solutions have also dissimilarly affected different economic sectors, with people with **lower income facing once more the biggest downsides**.

A study from Oxfam and the Stockholm Environmental Institute indicates [the richest 10% of the world's population were responsible for more than half of the cumulative carbon emissions between 1990 and 2015, whilst the poorest 50% of the world population were responsible for just 7% of the cumulative emissions](#). However, measures such as **Carbon Taxing** affect disproportionately the lower classes. Whilst effective in mitigating the emissions of greenhouse gases, the increase in taxes of electricity and gas, for example, has a higher impact on lower-income families. Moreover, the closure of “polluting enterprises”, such as power plants and refineries, leaves thousands of people without jobs. It could be argued that new jobs are also being created in regard to clean energies. However, the set of required skills is often not the same, not allowing a direct and smooth transition. These are some of the main reasons for the rise of “anti-green” protests, with the most flagrant example being [the “Yellow Vests” in France in 2018](#).

Nowadays, we are facing a period of increased economic volatility, with a potential financial crisis awaiting in the next years for most Members of the EU. Some argue that now it's the time to **invest in greener technologies** and use this opportunity to revolutionise our economy. In fact, [the Recovery Plan for Europe intends to invest 373.9 billion euros in Natural Resources and the Environment](#). In spite of this, there are some that argue that part of this money could be invested in preserving the economic stability of the EU, rather than investing in new markets.

Lastly, another crucial aspect of the fight to reverse climate change is that it needs to be a **joint effort between every country in the world**. It will not mean much if Europe is indeed the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 if economic superpowers such as China and the USA, whose [combined net emissions of greenhouse gases amount to 42% of the world's total emissions](#), do not significantly alter their policymaking in order to address these issues. With [the USA re-entering the Paris Agreement](#) and [China announcing its intention to achieve carbon-neutrality by 2060](#), there is hope that change is going to start speeding up and that a green economy might be possible in time to save our planet.

Outlook

Climate change is a complex problem, with several different aspects. Logically, our response to climate change can also be very complex. **It should address all different areas that affect our greenhouse gas emissions**, in order to achieve a net reduction of 55% by 2030 and climate neutrality by 2050.

There are no perfect solutions. While each solution has its setbacks, **inaction is simply not an option**. Not acting right now will cause irreparable damage to the environment, and seriously harm our quality of life in the future, **with a higher frequency of catastrophic events, extinction of entire biomes, rise of the sea level, and increase in the average temperature**.

What should be the areas of action of the EU strategy to mitigate the causes and effects of climate change? Should the focus be on taxing greenhouse gas emissions or on rewarding environmentally friendly initiatives? How can the EU ensure a balance between investing in greener technologies and assuring a just transition for workers in “polluting companies”? How can the EU cement its role as a leader in Climate Change policy making and help other countries achieve their own climate goals?

Further Readings

- [How the EU Fights Climate Change: The Race Against the Clock, European Parliament](#), A video showing the urgency in fighting climate change and what actions have already been implemented by the EU in this area.
- [EU Climate Action and the European Green Deal](#), The European Commission action plan and key legislation regarding the European Green Deal and the 2030 and 2050 climate and energy frameworks.
- [Fossil CO₂ Emissions in the Post-Covid-19 Era, Corinne Le Quéré, Glen P. Peters, Pierre Friedlingstein, Robbie M. Andrew, Josep G. Canadell, Steven J. Davis, Robert B. Jackson & Matthew W. Jones](#), An article about the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic in global CO₂ emissions, as well as what trends are expected to follow.
- [Europe’s Plan to Become the First Carbon-Neutral Continent, Ursula von der Leyen](#), An explanation of the EU’s plan, detailing the challenges and opportunities, to transition an entire continent to clean energy.
- [The EU Climate Law Explained, EURACTIV](#), An explanation of what the EU Climate Law does, how it works, and what are its criticisms.
- [China and US Pledge Climate Change Commitment, Roger Harrabin](#), An article analysing the recent commitment by the two biggest economies in the world to increase their efforts to fight climate change.

DROI

Committee on Human Rights

Refugees' physical and mental healthcare needs

With the COVID-19 posing a big challenge for many of Europe's healthcare systems and disproportionately affecting vulnerable communities such as refugees, their access to medical care is further hindered by practical obstacles such as language barriers and improper reception facilities. What measures should be taken by the Member States to safeguard the physical and mental healthcare needs of asylum seekers, and to also ensure unhindered access to other essential services following their arrival in the EU?

By Lazar Tripinovic

Topic Overview

Committee on Human Rights (DROI)

With the COVID-19 posing a big challenge for many of Europe's healthcare systems and disproportionately affecting vulnerable communities such as refugees, their access to medical care is further hindered by practical obstacles such as language barriers and improper reception facilities. What measures should be taken by the Member States to safeguard the physical and mental healthcare needs of asylum seekers, and to also ensure unhindered access to other essential services following their arrival in the EU?

Chairperson: Lazar Tripinović (RS)

Topic in a nutshell

Refugees globally present the most vulnerable part of the population. Many living in overcrowded areas, such as refugee camps and poor neighborhoods, often lack basic needs such as [clean, potable water, proper housing, and legal protection](#). In the face of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic which turned the world upside down, refugees find themselves at special risk. For many refugees, regardless of their country of residence, **social distance or regular hand-washing presents a luxury**. Moreover, the situation in the refugee camps all across Europe is even worse. Overcrowded camps [do not allow for any kinds of distancing and are now being overlooked](#) because of the whole pandemic. Moreover, Europe's human rights are being challenged, by the pushbacks on its external borders in Hungary and [Croatia](#). While the EU does have the right to deport illegal immigrants, which moral obligation should it be held to in face of a double crisis - refugee and pandemic?

More than a year after the World Health Organisation declared the COVID-19 pandemic, many countries are still struggling with the challenges it brought, such as the [economy](#) and [vaccination](#). Bram Frouws, head of the Mixed Migration Center noted that “Usually, when economies go into recession people become a bit more conservative or nationalistic, and ‘let's care for our own population first’. It's not a very [conducive environment to progressive approaches towards migration](#).”

[Another factor reported by the European Commission is the fact that most of the refugees currently seeking asylum in the European Commission come from countries facing economic downturn, rather than conflict](#). Consequently, they are more likely to **work for low wages, or even work unregistered**.

Unsecured livelihood can **lead to malnutrition, deterioration of immunity, and increase the potential [COVID-19](#)**. In addition, European Commission reports that **in 2019 most residence permits were issued for work and family reasons**, but nevertheless, non-EU citizens were overrepresented [solely in the low-paid sectors, such as cleaners, building workers, mining, etc.](#) Certain EU countries decided to vaccinate undocumented migrants, but many passed [no legislation on this issue](#).

Figure taken from the [European Commission](#) indicating the reasons for the issuance of the residence permits in the EU in 2019.

Key Terms

- **Refugee** is “A person who owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country; or who, not having a nationality and being outside the country of his former habitual residence as a result of such events, is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to return to it.”¹
- **Migrant** is someone who has moved to another country for any reason, such as to find work.
- **Asylum seeker** is a person who has left their country of origin and formally applied for asylum in another country but whose application has not yet been concluded.
- **Residence permit** is the document allowing a foreign national to reside in a country for a fixed or indefinite length of time.

¹ The definition of a refugee according to The [1951 United Nations Convention](#) Relating to the Status of Refugees.

- **Asylum** is the protection granted by a state to someone who has left their home country as a political refugee.
- **Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)** is the UN's document from 1948, widely accepted as the fundamental norms of human rights that everyone should respect and protect for the first time in human history spelled out basic civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights that all human beings should enjoy.
- **European Declaration of Human Rights (EDHR)** is a document signed by all the member states of the Council of Europe in 1950, protecting the rights of the citizens of 47 Member States of the Council.

Stakeholders & Measures in place

[Member States \(MS\)](#) refers to 27 countries that are members of the EU.

[European Commission \(EC\)](#) is one of the EU's three main governing bodies. The EC helps to shape the **EU's overall strategy, proposes new EU laws and policies, monitors their implementation, and manages the EU budget**. It also plays a significant role in supporting international development and delivering aid. Members of the EC are chosen by the MS and approved by the European Parliament.

European Commission published **New Pact on Migration and Asylum**² in 2020, which focused on effective measures, responsibility and solidarity, as means of dealing with challenges regarding migration and asylum. Among the main solutions, the EC has found: **compulsory pre-entry screening, independent monitoring mechanism, relocation of recently-arrived persons**.

Another important policy proposed by the EC is described by [search and rescue at sea](#) as 'a legal obligation and moral duty'.

[European Parliament](#) has 3 roles: It **debates legislation, passes or rejects laws, and amendments** (but not in all cases). Laws must also be passed by the Council of the EU in order to become law. It is the only body in the Union that is directly elected by the citizens.

[European Council](#) defines the **EU's overall political direction and priorities**. It is **not one** of the EU's legislating institutions, so it **does not negotiate or adopt EU laws**. Instead, **it sets the EU's policy agenda**, traditionally by adopting 'conclusions' during European Council meetings which identify issues of concern and actions to take.

² You can find the link to the website in the **Further Readings**.

[The World Health Organisation \(WHO\)](#) is a special body of the UN, that acts as a coordinating body of international public health.

[Draft Global Action Plan ‘Promoting the Health of Refugees and Migrants’](#) adopted at [72th World Health Assembly](#)³ in May 2019, emphasises the importance of the healthcare needs of refugees and migrants. The [WHO Constitution of 1948](#)⁴ ratified **international human rights standards and conventions to** protect the rights of migrants and refugees, including their right to health.

[The United Nations General Assembly](#) is the chief deliberative, policymaking, and representative organ of the UN. It is a unique multilateral forum composed of all 193 UN Members.

[The Universal Declaration of Human Rights \(UDHR\)](#) in Articles 13, 14, 22, and 25 promises everyone the rights of movement, residence, asylum from persecution, medical care, and social service.

Key challenges

- Many EU Member States face **shortages of medical equipment**, such as vaccines, face masks, hospital beds, etc. The **economic downturn** and challenges to the whole economic system is a hot topic. Ensuring **physical health** to the refugees in this period is a special challenge. [Some countries](#) have explicitly included **non-residents**, even non-registered migrants in the vaccination programmes, while others struggle even to provide enough vaccines to their citizens. Should the European Commission consider passing the **EU-wide policy** on dealing with the non-EU citizens on its territory? [The unresolved refugee crisis](#) and the rise of right-oriented politics across the continent should also be considered here.
- Additionally, most countries do not have laws that would protect **foreign citizens’** healthcare needs. During the pandemics, the importance of **collective awareness and responsibility** proved crucial in order to contain the virus. Many migrants and refugees do not have legal **residence permits** or have expired ones, which results in their [inability to seek medical help](#). This is not only dangerous to themselves but **can be threatening to the system as a whole**. How could the Member States protect the healthcare needs of the refugees and preserve the

³**World Health Assembly** is the decision-making body of WHO, whose main functions are to determine the policies of the Organisation, appoint the Director-General, supervise financial policies, and review and approve the proposed programme budget. It is held annually in Geneva.

⁴The **WHO Constitution** presents the guiding rules and principles of the WHO. The Constitution was adopted by the International Health Conference in 1946 and entered into force in 1948.

COVID-19 measures in the whole society? If this influences the medical safety of the whole population, which approaches could each Member State apply and should there be an EU-wide policy/agreement tackling this issue?

- Having in mind that Article 1 of [ECHR](#) states **Human dignity is inviolable**. It must be respected and protected, is the decision of the EU to allow **relocation** of recently-arrived persons, as one of the **flexible options** for the Member States justified? While it might not present an obvious clash of interests, the possibility that certain people will be reallocated might appear dehumanising, or taking away from their individual autonomy and right to free movement. Many countries claim they do not have the [capacity to host](#) refugees and migrants. Due to economic, social, or territorial reasons, [the policy of relocation](#)⁵ can maybe be justified. On the other hand, there have been more than [18000 refugee children](#) (unaccompanied and under-aged) that were lost in Europe in the period 2018-2020, of which many were never found. Coming back to the horrors occurring in the **home countries** of the refugees, is the stand that the 'lack of capacity' is a legitimate excuse, and can it be trusted that relocation is legitimate means of dealing with this issue?

⁵The **policy of relocation** is a policy that is a part of the [New Pact on Migration and Asylum](#).

An infographic taken by the [Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants](#) that indicates the countries with European vaccine strategies that include and exclude undocumented migrants and refugees.

Outlook

While discussing the **influence of the pandemic** on the **refugees** and how to ensure their **physical and mental welfare**, two stands must be taken. The refugees and the EU. The EU must protect its citizens and stand behind its **values**. Gaps between the Member States in the economy and healthcare system, combined with traditions and demographics, can influence how the countries treat residing refugees and asylum seekers. Moreover, some countries are worried that pandemic is already too hard to deal with, that giving a special place in the COVID measures to non-citizens will have a **harmful effect** on the rest of the population. Nevertheless, rule of law means respecting everyone's human rights. Considering the background and the fear of persecution and economic downturn in the countries of origin, and the policies regarding the importance of the **medical needs** of the refugees

and healthcare for everyone, as stated by the UN, the human rights of the **asylum seekers** in the EU must not be neglected. How should the EU **balance** its approach to this complex issue?

Further Readings

- [New Pact on Migration and Asylum, European Commission](#), A comprehensive overview of new policies and approaches to migration and asylum in the EU,
- [Matteo Salvini to face trial over standoff with migrant rescue ship, The Guardian](#), An article on Matteo Salvini's trial over his decision to prevent a rescue ship with refugees to sail at the Italian port of Lampedusa,
- [European Convention on Human Rights, By the European Court of Human Rights](#), The convention signed by all the Member States of the Council of Europe,
- [One year on: How the pandemic has affected refugees, asylum seekers, and migration, The New Humanitarian](#), An article on the global impact of COVID-19 pandemic on refugees and the migrant population,
- [Refugees and undocumented migrants must be vaccinated, NGOs warn, Deutsche Welle](#), An article on the vaccination of the migrant in the European countries
- [Human Mobility and Human Rights in the COVID-19 Pandemic: Principles of Protection for Migrants, Refugees, and Other Displaced Persons, International Journal of Refugee Law](#), An Oxford's academic article that provides a great overview on how human rights are affected during the COVID-19 pandemic.

FEMM

Committee on Women's Rights and Gender Equality

Domestic Violence & Gender Equality

Cry for help: Domestic violence has elevated during lockdown with the European Commission noting a dramatic increase in reports by 60% around Europe. How can the EU protect women's human rights and gender equality during a pandemic?

By Stefanos Francis

Topic Overview

Committee on Women's Rights and Gender Equality (FEMM)

Cry for help: Domestic violence has elevated during lockdown with the European Commission noting a dramatic increase in reports by 60% around Europe. How can the EU protect women's human rights and gender equality during a pandemic?

Chairperson: Stefanos Francis (CY)

Topic in a nutshell

Throughout the years, women have fallen victims to domestic violence crimes at an alarming rate. It is estimated that around [35%-70% of women who are victimized by Intimate Partner Violence \(IPV\) are diagnosed with depression every year](#), accounting for about [12% of women in the general population](#). Victims of domestic violence are often associated with [Post Traumatic Stress Disorder \(PTSD\)](#), substance abuse, and oftentimes suicidal tendencies.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, it is believed that [Domestic Violence crimes have risen at a 20% rate](#), due to the fact that victims are trapped in their homes alongside their abusers. According to the [World Health Organization \(WHO\)](#)¹ [1 in 3 females globally have been put through Intimate Partner Violence](#) either mentally, physically, or sexually and such acts can increase chances of mental, sexual, or reproductive issues. According to the [Center for Disease Control and Prevention \(CDC\)](#)² data from the USA, crime reports estimate that [1 in 5 homicide victims are a result of IPV](#) and over half of them are women killed by a current or former male intimate partner. Worldwide it is estimated that as many as [38% of all murders of women are committed by intimate partners](#).

Even if a woman manages to survive their abuser the life-long effects on the survivor are prominent and materialize in the form of PTSD in [31% to 84.4% of survivors](#). During periods of crisis, a huge surge in cases of gender violence was noted both during and after said crises.

¹ **World Health Organization (WHO)** is a bilateral agency of the United Nations composed of 194 Member States that strives to combat diseases and coordinate international health within the United Nations system.

² **Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)** is the national public health agency of the United States of America that aims in protecting America from health, safety and security threats, both foreign and inside the U.S. The CDC fights disease and supports communities and citizens to do the same.

Key Terms

- **Intimate Partner Violence (IPV)** describes physical violence, sexual violence, stalking, or psychological harm by a current or former partner or spouse. This type of violence can occur among heterosexual or same-sex couples and does not require sexual intimacy.
- **Sexual Orientation, Gender Identity and Expression, and Sex Characteristics (SOGIESC)** is an umbrella term used in order to refer to minority groups that differentiate between them using one of the characteristics described by the term.

Stakeholders & Measures in place

[The Domestic Violence Prevention Enhancement and Leadership Through Alliances \(DELTA\)](#), is an Impact program overseen by the CDC that funds State Domestic Violence Coalitions in order to implement strategies that prevent IPV. It also runs host to a coordinated community response team that is composed of diverse sectors (eg. public health, law enforcement, etc) in order to prevent and respond to such crimes and provide support and relief to the women that fall victim to them.

In 2019, the WHO and [UN Women³ alongside other UN bilateral agencies published RESPECT Women](#), a framework for preventing violence against women aimed specifically at policymakers. Each letter of the word “RESPECT” stands for one of the seven strategies. Relationship skills strengthening; Empowerment of women; Services ensured; Poverty reduced; Enabling environments (schools, workplaces, public spaces) created; Child and adolescent abuse prevented; and Transformed attitudes, beliefs, and norms.

[The Belém do Pará Convention \(MESECVI\)](#),⁴ The Committee of Experts of the Follow-up Mechanism of the Belém do Pará Convention (MESECVI) has published a [set of guidelines](#) that highlights the position women are put in while being socially isolated with the perpetrators and requests States to carry out all the necessary means to combat IPV while emphasizing on some of the most effective counters to this shadow pandemic.

³ **UN Women** is a bilateral agency of the United Nations that focuses on the welfare of women inside the Member-States of the UN.

⁴ **The Belém do Pará Convention (MESECVI)** is an international human rights instrument concluded within the Organisation of American States (OAS), which calls for the establishment of mechanisms for protecting and defending women's rights, and for combating violence against women's physical, sexual, and psychological integrity.

Key challenges

Healthcare access for the victims of such heinous crimes as IPV has become increasingly difficult during the COVID-19 pandemic as [most hospitals](#) and health facilities have shut down to the public in order to mitigate the risk of inter-facility infections. While that is a good practice to reduce the spread of the virus it has come as a wound to **those suffering from domestic abuse as they are unable to seek professional medical help** for any possible injuries that come as a direct consequence of the violence.

Moreover, due to the shutdown of most government facilities to the public, **it is rapidly becoming harder for victims to seek out legal help or turn out governmental agencies**, forcing them to remain under the abuse of their perpetrators and worsening the risk of injuries and the possibility of mental health issues or suicidal tendencies to arise, seeing as the victims who suffer under the oppression of abusive male partners are indirect declines any and all professional help.

Additionally, [the discrimination of women based on sex and gender is inextricably linked with other factors that affect women, such as race, ethnicity, religion or belief, health, status, age, class, caste, and sexual orientation, and gender identity](#). Discrimination on the basis of sex or gender may affect women belonging to such groups to a different degree or in different ways than men. However, the mainstreaming of SOGIESC issues in gender equality agenda, as well as legal framework and mechanisms directed at tackling domestic and gender-based violence, remains a challenge.

Figure 1
Countries with Legislation on Domestic Violence

Source: Figure created by the authors using data from World Bank Group, *Women, Business and the Law* 2018 (Washington, D.C.: World Bank, 2018).

A figure showing the countries with legislation on domestic violence by the [World Bank Group](#).

Following up on what was previously said, it is important that we understand the [social stigma](#) that comes with domestic abuse and negatively impacts the female population. Many women are afraid of reaching out to official resources, fearing that their perpetrators will catch a whiff of what they are

attempting to do and harass them further, oftentimes concluding in unavoidable extreme physical abuse as a way of "punishment". Such means of oppression force victims to keep quiet and only worsen their situations. While many services offer anonymous help without recording personal data it becomes increasingly harder to track down and prevent such cases and as such creates an endless circle of futile attempts for women to escape horrid circumstances of abuse.

Outlook

Overall, throughout the years' domestic violence against women has been a problem that's been tormenting our world but during the recent COVID-19 pandemic the **increase in IPV**s has put many women at an unprecedented amount of risk. It is of vital importance that the world unionises and rises up against this shadow pandemic that's been plaguing our world. Men should be held liable for their actions and governments of Member-States should be held responsible for letting their female population down. How do we, as modern citizens, act against these heinous crimes? What can our governments do to not only provide relief to the victims of such horrid and inhumane crimes but also prevent them from even happening in the first place? Is this what our civilizations strive to be? How does modern Europe protect its citizens and ensure that their basic human lives are not violated?

Further Readings

Audiovisual:

- [RESPECT - to end violence against women, World Health Organisation](#), A video showcasing the framework in a creative way and encouraging people to take action.
- [WHO leadership speaks about R.E.S.P.E.C.T, World Health Organisation](#), A video composed of the leadership of the WHO highlighting the importance of the aspects of the RESPECT framework.

Articles:

- [Delta Impact Theory of Change, CDC](#), An article on the impact program that aims in decreasing risk factors associated with IPV and increase protective factors that prevent it.
- [A New Covid-19 Crisis: Domestic Abuse Rises Worldwide, Amanda Taub](#), An article consisting of multiple cases of domestic abuse during lockdown and expert's opinions and sayings.

Publications:

- [COVID-19 and violence against women, World Health Organisation](#), A publication emphasizing the interconnected effects of the Covid-19 pandemic and IPV's.

- [Guidelines for protecting the rights of women and girls during the COVID-19 pandemic, Amnesty International](#), A publication highlighting the importance of preserving and protecting women's human rights from being violated and detailing the work of agencies.
- [Violence against women a priority health issue, World Health Organisation](#), A detailed study conducted by the WHO showcasing the different dimensions of women abuse.
- [Celebrating 25 years of the mandate of the Special Rapporteur on violence against women: Call for submissions, Eastern European Coalition for LGBT+ Equality](#), A mandate focusing on the domestic abuse women that identify as LGBT+ face by their intimate partners and how it can be tackled.

An infographic from the [WHO](#) showcasing statistics regarding IPV in women.

CULT

Committee on Culture and Education

Effect of the pandemic on education

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected educational systems worldwide, leading to the near-total closures of schools, universities and colleges with over 100 million children falling below the minimum proficiency level in reading as a result of the health crisis. What measures can be taken by the Member States to ensure that the youth will receive the best academic level possible during the pandemic?

By Beatriz Soares

Topic Overview

Committee on Culture and Education (CULT)

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected educational systems worldwide, leading to the near-total closures of schools, universities, and colleges with over 100 million children falling below the minimum proficiency level in reading as a result of the health crisis.

What measures can be taken by the Member States to ensure that the youth will receive the best academic level possible during the pandemic?

Chairperson: Beatriz Soares (PT)

Topic in a nutshell

Since last year, Europe was compelled to adapt to different educational systems from the traditional teacher-student dynamics. In a digital format, **disparities are more evident than ever** and vary from access to the internet, computers, and even a supportive and healthy environment. From 2018 to 2020, the number of European households with internet access went from **88% to 91%**, and although this change is positive, there are still a lot of citizens **without** a proper **connection to the world wide web**, or to a **personal computer**.

Even with access to the means mentioned above, many **parents do not have the digital literacy** or the time to **provide a supportive and stable environment that is required** to adapt to this new mode of instruction. In most European countries, children from a **lower social-economic class** are more prone to the **lack of reading opportunities and a quiet space to learn**. Independently of the income, a certain country produces, parents in the poorest households have more difficulty helping their children with homework.

Given that **education is one of the biggest pillars of our society**, the learning loss, in the short and long term, is expected to be great and beyond education. Situations of **food insecurity, economic instability, mental health, and even violence towards women and children** are some of the expected effects of the education crisis happening in the world and in the European Union (EU). So the time has come to try to solve these issues and think of innovative alternatives that prove themselves to **mirror the European values of equality, cooperation, and discrimination**.

Key Terms

- **Minimum Proficiency Level (MPL)** is the benchmark of basic knowledge in a domain (mathematics, reading, etc.) measured through learning assessments.
- **Digital Literacy** refers to an individual's ability to find, evaluate, and compose clear information through writing and other media on various digital platforms.

Stakeholders & Measures in place

- **European Commission (EC)** - Each country in the European Union manages its own education system, so the EC plays more of a **supporting role**. It offers a forum for cooperation between countries and tries to **improve coherence in education policies**. It funds various initiatives that support education in Europe, from ensuring the recognition of qualifications abroad to promoting success stories. The main project related to this issue is a free online tool, [SELFIE](#), that **provides free resources for both teachers and students**. The **Digital Education Action Plan** implemented by the EC was updated this year and has [set a goal for 70% of people between the ages of 16 and 74 to have basic digital skills by 2025](#).
- **European Centre for Economic, Policy Analysis and Affairs (ECEPAA)** is a Belgian non-profit organization specialized in the fields of **research, education, youth, migration, entrepreneurship, culture, and social inclusion**. ECEPAA implements and develops **assistance projects** at the local, national and international level in the aforementioned fields in addition to conducting policy-oriented research. Some of their projects include [I.H.A.V.E.T.](#), which promotes a more proactive attitude from parents that aids with the educational performance of their children in order to reduce the dropout levels.
- **European Schoolnet** is a non-profit organization that focuses on supporting education stakeholders in Europe in the **transformation of education processes for 21st century digitised societies**. They identify and test promising **innovative practices**, share evidence about their impact, and support the usage of said practices. One example of this is the [European Schoolnet Academy](#) where teachers from all around Europe can share their experiences, and attend free online courses regarding digital literacy.

- **Ministries of Education** are national entities responsible for the execution, evaluation, and coordination of education-related legislation. One example of a national initiative is the [Estudo em Casa](#) promoted by the Portuguese government and the national TV channel, where **lessons from all the compulsory levels of education were broadcasted**.

An Infographic taken from [The impact of COVID-19 on education - insights from education at glance 2020](#) OECD report.

Key challenges

Digital literacy on teachers

According to the **Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)**¹ Teaching and Learning International Survey in 2018, only **39% of educators felt prepared to use digital means** in their everyday teaching, with significant differences between the Member States. Since last year, educators saw themselves with no other choice but to engage in digital schooling to provide education and training. Teachers had to quickly adjust their teaching methods and learning expectations. New ways

¹The **Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)** is an intergovernmental economic organization that works as a platform to compare policy experiences, seek answers to common problems, identify good practices and coordinate domestic and international policies of its members. Although the OECD doesn't have executive power over the decisions made, it is recognised as a highly influential organization worldwide.

of teaching to **cover as much of the curriculum as possible** were developed and teachers must be as literate as possible on these topics **to ensure the quality of education.**

Teachers are the key to the successful implementation of distance learning. Almost [50% of the UNESCO² surveyed education systems](#) are providing additional teacher training to properly prepare for distance teaching. This crisis has increased the need to improve the digital skills of educators and at the same time has opened a range of possibilities to both **improve digital literacy and to create new means of distance learning.**

Students don't have the means to access online school

A [study from the OECD](#) shows that a large number of young Europeans either don't have access to a computer or to a quiet place to study. And even if there is a computer per household, families with children on different learning levels, may not have a device per child, making it harder to follow all classes. This education problem now has a **socio-economic aspect**, children and young people from **poorer backgrounds have their access to education** called to question by their personal belongings. Before the pandemic struck, socio-economic discrepancies were already a major issue regarding education, but now that students rely on expensive digital means to attain it, differences only became deeper and a bigger concern to what is one of the more pressing issues in the EU.

[These statistics from OECD](#) show that even if a **high percentage of students have access**, there is still a long way to go before **online school is not a source of discrimination and social differences.**

²**UNESCO** is the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization that seeks to build peace through international cooperation in Education, the Sciences and Culture. UNESCO develops educational tools to help people live as global citizens free of hate and intolerance.

CULT

Committee on Culture and Education

A chart by the [European Commission](#) indicates the percentage of 15-year-old students in the EU that reported having a computer at home for school.

A chart by the [European Commission](#) indicates the percentage of 15-year-old students in the EU that reported having a quiet place to study.

Another problem is that many children **do not have support at home** regarding technical issues that may arise or help with homework. Here we can see the percentage of individuals with children at home and their various levels of digital literacy.

A chart that indicates the level of digital skills in EU households with children by [Eurostat \(2019\) - Percentage of individuals \(16-24\) living in households with children \(0-16\) by digital skills level, country, and EU level.](#)

While students on upper education levels may already have the skills needed to work independently, younger learners are particularly penalized in this regard. [Younger students need additional support and guidance from parents and carers, including limiting their exposure to ‘screen time’ and passive usage of devices.](#)³ If this problem is not tackled, this generation will have a deficit in the fundamental education they are given on primary levels, **it may affect their development and ability to succeed once they move on to upper learning levels.**

Lower quality of education

With all the situations that were mentioned above, it is only expectable that education suffers greatly from it. According to the United Nations⁴, over [100 million children will fall below the minimum proficiency](#) level in reading due to the impact of COVID-19 school closures. This may turn into a generational problem, with university students having almost **half of their course on a digital format**, there are competencies that **require on-site learning to be properly integrated.**

The same [UNESCO report](#) finds that a return to the **pre-pandemic pathway may take a decade** but that **recovery could occur by 2024 if exceptional efforts are made to provide remedial classes and catch-up strategies.**

Outlook

Even though research efforts are underway, at present, solid data is missing on whether and how the distance and online teaching and learning practices put in place ensured **effective and equitable access** to quality learning opportunities for all. In order to do so, there are multiple fields that need to be improved upon, the more stressful issue is to ensure **access for all**, both a stable internet connection and the means to access it. A result of the lack of this equity is the **reduction of proficiency levels** on younger students that are learning the basics of the education they will have in the future. In order to, teachers also need to be as skilled as possible to ensure that the future generation of European leaders receives the **best education** Europe has to offer.

The EU has a key role in ensuring that every citizen sees their right to education fulfilled and not impair the learning of students from lower socio-economic classes.

³ **Section 3.1** Challenges in managing remote emergency education **page 17 to 21.**

⁴The **United Nations** are an international organization created in 1945 after world war II to be a platform where nations can gather together, discuss common problems and find shared solutions.

Therefore, how should the EU respond to the lack of digital literacy in teachers? What can the Member States do to minimize the increasing gap between students in higher and lower socio-economic classes? Which means should be developed to ensure that the academic levels of education aren't lost in a digital format?

Further Readings

Audiovisual:

- [Podcast: Education and coronavirus, European Investment Bank, Anna Canato](#) - A podcast produced by the European Investment Bank and with Anna Canato, head of education and public research at the European Investment Bank that talks about the several issues related to the effect of the pandemic to the educational systems.
- [SELFIE tool: Supporting schools for teaching in the digital age, European Commission](#) - A video that explains the SELFIE initiative.
- [Schools, education, and COVID-19, OECD](#) - An explanatory video that puts into perspective the reopening and the functioning of education during the pandemic.

Articles & Publications:

- [Digital Education Action Plan Fact Sheet, European Commission](#) - The Digital Education Action Plan set by the European Commission for the period of 2021-2027 with the main goal is resetting education and training for the digital age.
- [Educational inequalities in Europe and physical school closures during COVID-19, European Commission](#) - A briefing on the main issues covid-19 has brought upon education.
- [The Impact of Covid-19 on Schools in Europe, ECEPAA](#) - An article based on ECEPAA's take on how COVID-19 has affected education in Europe.
- [An EU education system that works for everyone, The Parliament Magazine](#) - An article reflecting on how the education system should adapt after COVID-19.

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